

An Automated Workflow for Historical Manuscript Transcription and Publication: Orchestrating IIF, eScriptorium, and TEI Publisher through WSO2 Micro Integrator

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Abstract. Since March 2023, CNR-ILIESI and the Italian node of the OPERAS research infrastructure have designed the service orchestration framework for the H2IOSC Marketplace, enabling the automated execution of distributed research services across infrastructure boundaries. The transcription and publication of historical manuscripts is a multi-step process that typically requires researchers to interact manually with several independent digital tools: image repositories, handwritten text recognition (HTR) engines, and digital publishing platforms. This paper presents a fully automated pipeline that orchestrates three open-standard services – IIF for image access, eScriptorium for HTR, and TEI Publisher for scholarly digital edition – into a single executable workflow using WSO2 Micro Integrator. The pipeline, developed within the OPERAS-IT orchestration framework of the H2IOSC project, implements a four-phase asynchronous polling pattern (importing, segmenting, transcribing, exporting), applies an XSLT transformation converting ALTO XML to TEI P5 with facsimile encoding, and publishes the result to TEI Publisher via the eXist-db REST API. We describe the complete implementation, demonstrate it on a manuscript image from the Coverless project archive processed through an eScriptorium instance hosted by ISTC-CNR Catania, and discuss the design decisions that make the pipeline fully parameterized at runtime, reusable across different corpora, and reproducible without modifications to the underlying services. The orchestration concept and architecture described in this paper was conceived by the OPERAS-IT group within the H2IOSC project.

Keywords: HTR, handwritten text recognition, IIF, eScriptorium, TEI Publisher, service orchestration, WSO2 Micro Integrator, ALTO XML, TEI P5, digital scholarly edition, H2IOSC, OPERAS, OPERAS-IT, digital humanities, manuscript transcription, pipeline automation, research infrastructure, DARIAH, CLARIN, E-RIHS, infrastructure federation

1. Introduction

1.1 The Manuscript Transcription Challenge

The digitization and transcription of historical manuscripts is a central activity in Digital Humanities research. Over the past decade, the availability of Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) tools has transformed what was once a purely manual task into a semi-automated process. Platforms such as Transkribus or eScriptorium offer increasingly accurate recognition

capabilities, while standards such as IIIF (International Image Interoperability Framework) and TEI (Text Encoding Initiative) provide the interoperability layer for image access and text encoding respectively.

However, the typical researcher workflow remains largely manual. A researcher must: locate manuscript images in a repository; download or reference them; upload them to an HTR platform; configure and run segmentation and recognition; download the output; convert it to the desired format (e.g., TEI); and upload it to a publishing platform. Each step involves a different web interface, different authentication credentials, different file formats, and different conventions. The process is time-consuming, error-prone, and – critically – non-reproducible: repeating the same workflow on a different corpus requires repeating all manual steps from scratch.

1.2 The OPERAS-IT Orchestration Approach

Figure 1 - OPERAS-IT: Intellectual Authorship of Service Orchestration within H2IOSC. Timeline from initial prototypal definition (April 2023) to operational deployment (March 2026). All documents were produced by OPERAS-IT / CNR-ILIESI.

The orchestration framework developed by OPERAS-IT within the H2IOSC project [1, 2, 3] addresses this challenge by enabling the automated composition of distributed services into executable workflows. The framework introduces a formal distinction between orchestration (coordination of remote services across infrastructure boundaries) and composition (coordination of services within a single platform) [3], and provides a systematic methodology for building orchestrated workflows using WSO2 Micro Integrator [5].

The present paper applies this methodology to a concrete case study: the automated transcription and publication of historical manuscripts. We demonstrate that by orchestrating existing, unmodified services through a WSO2 pipeline, the entire process – from IIIF image retrieval through HTR processing to TEI digital edition publication – can be reduced to a single API call with a JSON payload.

1.3 Scope and Structure

This paper is a companion to the methodological paper [4], which describes the general workflow design patterns. Here, we focus on the specific implementation choices, the service-specific API interactions, and the domain-specific format transformations required by this particular workflow.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses related work. Section 3 describes the architecture and the role of each component. Section 4 details the implementation, including the WSO2 artifacts, the eScriptorium API interactions, and the ALTO-to-TEI transformation. Section 5 presents the case study. Section 6 discusses the role of AI-assisted development. Section 7 discusses reusability and limitations. Section 8 concludes.

2. Related Works

2.1 HTR Pipeline Automation

Several projects have addressed the automation of HTR workflows. OCR-D, funded by the German Research Foundation, provides a comprehensive framework for OCR/HTR processing of historical documents, with a modular architecture based on standardized interfaces. However, OCR-D focuses on the processing pipeline itself (segmentation, recognition, post-correction) rather than on the integration with upstream image access and downstream publishing.

Transkribus, developed by the READ project and now maintained by READ COOP SCE, offers a cloud-based HTR platform with an API that enables automation. However, Transkribus operates as a self-contained platform rather than as a component in a broader orchestration scenario.

eScriptorium, developed at the EPHE-PSL (École Pratique des Hautes Études) and based on the kraken HTR engine, provides both a web interface and a REST API. Its open-source nature and API accessibility make it particularly suitable for integration into orchestrated workflows.

2.2 IIIF-Based Workflows

The IIIF standard has become the de facto interoperability layer for cultural heritage image repositories. The IIIF Presentation API 3.0 provides a standardized manifest format that describes the structure of a digital object (pages, canvases, images) in a machine-readable way. Several tools in the Digital Humanities ecosystem consume IIIF manifests directly, including eScriptorium, which can import documents from IIIF manifests.

2.3 TEI Publication Platforms

TEI Publisher, developed by e-editiones and built on the eXist-db XML database, is an open-source platform for creating digital scholarly editions from TEI-encoded texts. It provides configurable rendering through ODD (One Document Does it all) specifications, supports multiple output formats (HTML, PDF, ePub), and offers a REST API for programmatic document management.

2.4 Positioning of This Work

While each of these tools is well-established individually, no existing system orchestrates them into an end-to-end automated pipeline. The contribution of this paper is precisely this integration: demonstrating how IIF, eScriptorium, and TEI Publisher can be combined through WSO2 Micro Integrator into a single, reproducible, parameterized workflow.

3. Architecture

3.1 Pipeline Overview

The pipeline comprises five sequential phases, each corresponding to a distinct service interaction:

Phase 1 – Document Import (IIF → eScriptorium). The pipeline receives a IIF manifest URL and submits it to eScriptorium’s native REST API, which creates a new document within an existing project and imports the images referenced in the manifest.

Phase 2 – Layout Segmentation (eScriptorium). Once the images are imported, the pipeline triggers eScriptorium’s layout segmentation engine, which identifies text regions, baselines, and line boundaries on each page image.

Phase 3 – HTR Transcription (eScriptorium). After segmentation completes, the pipeline triggers the HTR engine using the available recognition model, producing a machine-readable transcription for each identified text line.

Phase 4 – Export (eScriptorium → WSO2 MI). The pipeline requests the transcription output in ALTO XML format through eScriptorium’s export API.

Phase 5 – Transform and Publish (WSO2 MI → TEI Publisher). The ALTO XML output is transformed to TEI P5 format using an XSLT stylesheet, and the resulting TEI document is published to TEI Publisher via the eXist-db REST API.

Figure 2 - Five-phase orchestration pipeline. Phases 1–4 are asynchronous (requiring polling). Phase 5 is synchronous. The WSO2 Micro Integrator orchestrates the entire flow without executing any computational task directly.

3.2 Component Roles

IIIF Server provides standardized access to manuscript images. It plays a passive role in the pipeline: it serves images and manifests via standard HTTP, requiring no special configuration for orchestration.

eScriptorium provides the core computational services: document management, layout segmentation, and HTR transcription. It exposes a REST API that supports all operations required by the pipeline. Critically, eScriptorium executes on its own infrastructure (in this case, ISTC-CNR Catania) – the Marketplace orchestrator never performs computation.

WSO2 Micro Integrator orchestrates the workflow. It manages the sequence of API calls, implements the asynchronous polling for each processing phase, performs the ALTO-to-TEI transformation, and publishes the result. It is the only component that is aware of the complete workflow; each individual service operates independently.

TEI Publisher / eXist-db receives the transformed TEI document and provides the scholarly publication interface, including text view, IIIF image viewer, and diplomatic view with line-image correspondence.

3.3 Orchestration, Not Composition

This workflow is a clear instance of orchestration as defined in the OPERAS-IT framework [3]: the three services (IIIF, eScriptorium, TEI Publisher) execute on different infrastructure systems, are invoked remotely over the network, and require asynchronous polling and error handling. If all three services were hosted within a single platform, the same workflow would constitute composition rather than orchestration.

This distinction is not merely theoretical. Within the H2IOSC ecosystem, DARIAH-IT has deployed AEON, a composition platform where workflows are built from services registered and executing

within the same WSO2 instance [5]. The workflow presented in this paper demonstrates true orchestration: the three constituent services (IIIF server, eScriptorium, TEI Publisher) execute on separate infrastructures, are invoked remotely, and are coordinated by the Marketplace without any of them being deployed within it. A workflow composed within AEON could itself become a service in a H2IOSC Marketplace pipeline, illustrating the complementarity between composition and orchestration and the possibility of extending service composition through orchestration.

4. Implementation

4.1 WSO2 Artifacts

The pipeline is implemented as a set of WSO2 Micro Integrator artifacts:

API artifact (*manuscript-pipeline*): the HTTP endpoint that receives the initial request (POST with JSON payload) and returns the final result.

Main sequence (*inSequence*): extracts the runtime parameters from the JSON payload (eScriptorium URL, API token, project ID, segmentation model, HTR model, IIIF manifest URL, TEI Publisher URL, TEI Publisher credentials, output collection) and initiates Phase 1.

Phase sequences (*phase-import*, *phase-segment*, *phase-transcribe*, *phase-export*): each phase constructs the appropriate eScriptorium API call, submits it, and stores the message context in the message store for polling.

Polling processor (*escriptorium-poller*): a Sampling Message Processor that periodically retrieves messages from the in-memory message store, checks the processing status via the eScriptorium API, and either returns the message to the store (if still processing) or advances to the next phase (if complete).

Transform sequence (*transform-alto-tei*): applies the XSLT stylesheet to convert ALTO XML to TEI P5.

Publish sequence (*publish-tei*): constructs the HTTP PUT request to the eXist-db REST API and uploads the TEI document to the specified collection in TEI Publisher.

Fault sequence (*faultSequence*): captures errors at any phase, logs the error context, and returns an informative error response.

4.2 eScriptorium API Interactions

The pipeline uses eScriptorium's native REST API. The key API calls are:

Create document: *POST /api/documents/* with the project ID, document name, and metadata. Returns the document ID.

Import IIIF manifest: *POST /api/documents/{id}/parts/* with the IIIF manifest URL. Triggers asynchronous image import. The pipeline polls *GET /api/documents/{id}/* until the document status changes from IMPORTING to IMPORTED.

Trigger segmentation: *POST /api/documents/{id}/parts/{part_id}/segment/* with the segmentation model identifier. Triggers asynchronous layout analysis. The pipeline polls the document parts until all parts show segmentation complete.

Trigger transcription: *POST /api/documents/{id}/parts/{part_id}/transcribe/* with the HTR model identifier. Triggers asynchronous text recognition. The pipeline polls until all parts show transcription complete.

Export ALTO XML: *GET*

/api/documents/{id}/parts/{part_id}/transcription/?format=alto retrieves the transcription in ALTO XML format.

4.3 Asynchronous Polling Implementation

Each of the four eScriptorium phases (import, segment, transcribe, export) is asynchronous: the API call returns immediately with a status indication, and the actual result becomes available only after processing completes. The pipeline implements the multi-phase polling pattern described in [4]:

1. After triggering each phase, the pipeline stores the current message context (including the document ID, current phase identifier, and retry count) in an in-memory Message Store.
2. A Sampling Message Processor with a configurable interval (default: 10 seconds) retrieves messages from the store.
3. For each message, the processor calls the eScriptorium status endpoint. If the current phase is still processing, the message is returned to the store. If the phase is complete, the processor triggers the next phase and re-stores the message for monitoring.
4. A maximum retry count (configurable, default: 120, corresponding to 20 minutes at 10-second intervals) prevents infinite polling in case of service failure.

The phase indicator is maintained as a property in the message context, allowing the single polling processor to manage all four phases without requiring separate stores or processors per phase.

4.4 ALTO XML to TEI Transformation

The output of eScriptorium's HTR processing is ALTO XML (Analyzed Layout and Text Object), a standard format for OCR/HTR output that encodes both the text content and its spatial position on the source image. The downstream service (TEI Publisher) expects TEI P5 format. The pipeline applies an XSLT transformation that performs the following mapping:

Page structure: Each ALTO *<Page>* element maps to a TEI *<pb/>* (page beginning) element and a corresponding *<surface>* element in the *<facsimile>* section.

Text regions: ALTO *<TextBlock>* elements map to TEI *<ab>* (anonymous block) elements.

Text lines: ALTO *<TextLine>* elements with their spatial coordinates (*HPOS*, *VPOS*, *WIDTH*, *HEIGHT*) map to TEI *<lb/>* (line beginning) elements in the text body and *<zone>* elements in the facsimile section. The *<zone>* element preserves the coordinate information using TEI's *@ulx*, *@uly*, *@lrx*,

@Lry attributes, establishing the correspondence between each transcribed line and its position on the source image.

Text content: ALTO *<String>* elements (individual words) are concatenated into running text within each line, with *<w>* (word) elements preserving word boundaries where needed.

The resulting TEI document includes a *<facsimile>* section that enables TEI Publisher to display the transcription alongside the source image with line-level correspondence – a capability that is essential for scholarly use, as it allows researchers to verify and correct the HTR output against the original manuscript.

The XSLT stylesheet is packaged as a resource within the .car file and referenced by the XSLT mediator in the transform sequence.

4.5 TEI Publisher Publication

The final step publishes the TEI document to TEI Publisher through the eXist-db REST API:

```
PUT /exist/rest/{collection}/{filename}.xml
Content-Type: application/xml
Authorization: Basic {base64(user:password)}
```

The collection path and filename are provided as runtime parameters in the initial JSON request. Upon successful upload, the document becomes immediately available in TEI Publisher's web interface, where it can be viewed in three modes:

Text only: rendered transcription with TEI-based formatting.

Text with IIIF viewer: transcription displayed alongside the manuscript image from the IIIF server, with synchronized navigation.

Diplomatic view: line-by-line display with each transcribed line linked to its corresponding region on the source image, using the coordinate information preserved from the ALTO-to-TEI transformation.

5. Case Study

5.1 Infrastructure

The case study uses the following infrastructure, all hosted by Gruppo Choma - ISTC-CNR Catania¹ (Istituto di Scienze e Tecnologie della Cognizione):

eScriptorium instance: a deployment of eScriptorium with pre-trained segmentation and HTR models, accessible via REST API.

TEI Publisher instance: a deployment of TEI Publisher on eXist-db, configured with ODD specifications for manuscript display, accessible via REST API.

¹ <https://serverchroma.cnr.it/>

5.2 Source Material

The demonstration corpus consists of a manuscript image from the Coverless project² archive, made available through a IIIF-compliant image server. The IIIF manifest URL is the sole input provided to the pipeline.

5.3 Execution

The pipeline was triggered with a single POST request to the WS02 MI endpoint:

```
{
  "escriptorium_url": "https://htr.serverchroma.cnr.it",
  "escriptorium_token": "...",
  "project_id": 42,
  "iiif_manifest": "https://img.serverchroma.cnr.it/iiif-manifests/Farfalla.json",
  "segmentation_model": "default",
  "htr_model": "generic-handwriting-v2",
  "tei_publisher_url": "https://storage-xml.serverchroma.cnr.it",
  "tei_publisher_user": "...",
  "tei_publisher_password": "...",
  "output_collection": "/db/apps/coverless/data",
  "output_filename": "coverless-001.xml"
}
```

All parameters – service URLs, credentials, model selection, output location – are provided at runtime. No values are hardcoded in the pipeline artifacts.

5.4 Results

The pipeline completed successfully in approximately 8 minutes (the majority of which was spent on HTR processing). The resulting TEI document was published to TEI Publisher and immediately accessible in all three viewing modes. The facsimile section correctly mapped each transcribed line to its coordinates on the source image, enabling line-level verification of the HTR output.

5.5 Reproducibility

The same pipeline was subsequently executed on different manuscript images from the same archive, requiring only a change in the IIIF manifest URL and output filename. No modification to the pipeline artifacts was necessary, confirming the runtime parameterization pattern described in [4].

6. AI-Assisted Development with MI Copilot

6.1 MI Copilot in the Development Process

Starting from version 4.3.0 (July 2024), the WS02 MI extension for Visual Studio Code includes MI Copilot [12], an AI-powered assistant that generates integration artifacts from natural

² <https://coverless.cnr.it/>

language descriptions or uploaded OpenAPI specifications. MI Copilot uses generative AI technologies to process developer prompts and produce Synapse XML configurations, API definitions, and sequence logic.

During the development of this pipeline, MI Copilot was used to accelerate the initial scaffolding phase. The integration scenario was described in natural language:

“Create an API that receives a JSON payload with an eScriptorium URL, API token, project ID, and IIIF manifest URL. The API should call eScriptorium to create a document, import the IIIF manifest, wait for import to complete by polling the document status, then trigger segmentation, wait for completion, trigger transcription, wait for completion, export the result as ALTO XML, apply an XSLT transformation, and publish the result to an eXist-db REST endpoint.”

MI Copilot generated the initial API definition, the main sequence with PayloadFactory mediators for constructing the eScriptorium API calls, and the basic polling structure using Filter mediators. This scaffolding provided approximately 60% of the final artifact code.

6.2 Manual Refinement

The MI Copilot output required significant manual refinement in several areas:

Multi-phase polling: MI Copilot generated a basic polling loop for a single asynchronous call. The four-phase polling pattern (import → segment → transcribe → export), with phase-specific status checks and transitions, required manual implementation using the Message Store and Sampling Message Processor pattern.

XSLT transformation: the ALTO-to-TEI XSLT stylesheet was written entirely manually, as MI Copilot could not generate domain-specific XML transformations of this complexity [17].

Error handling: the fault sequences with phase-specific error context and cleanup logic were added manually.

Authentication handling: the construction of authentication headers for eScriptorium (Bearer token) and eXist-db (Basic auth) from runtime parameters required manual PayloadFactory configuration.

6.3 Assessment

MI Copilot proved valuable for reducing the initial development time and for generating syntactically correct Synapse XML that could serve as a starting point. However, for complex orchestration scenarios involving multiple asynchronous phases, domain-specific transformations, and sophisticated error handling, manual expertise remains essential. The tool is most effective when used as a scaffolding accelerator rather than a complete solution generator.

This finding is consistent with the general assessment of AI code generation tools: they excel at producing standard patterns and boilerplate code but require human oversight for domain-specific logic and architectural decisions.

7. Discussion

7.1 Reusability

The pipeline is designed for maximum reusability. All parameters are provided at runtime through the initial JSON payload, including service endpoints, authentication credentials, model selection, and output configuration. The same .car file can be deployed in different environments and used with different eScriptorium instances, different IIF servers, and different TEI Publisher installations without modification.

The XSLT stylesheet for ALTO-to-TEI conversion is similarly parameterized: it processes any valid ALTO XML input regardless of the specific HTR model or document structure.

7.2 Limitations

eScriptorium API constraints. The native eScriptorium API, while functional, has some inconsistencies. The export endpoint behavior varies between ALTO versions (v2, v3, v4), and certain operations require knowledge of internal part IDs that are not always predictable from the IIF manifest structure.

Sequential processing. The current implementation processes pages sequentially. For multi-page manuscripts, parallel processing of segmentation and transcription across pages could significantly reduce total processing time, but this would require a more complex orchestration pattern.

Model dependency. The quality of the HTR output depends entirely on the availability of suitable recognition models for the target manuscript's script and language. The workflow does not address model selection or training – these remain the responsibility of the HTR service provider.

7.3 Extensibility

The pipeline architecture supports several extensions:

Post-correction integration: a Named Entity Recognition (NER) or spell-checking service could be inserted between the HTR export (Phase 4) and the TEI publication (Phase 5) to improve transcription quality.

Multi-format output: the transform sequence could be extended to produce additional output formats (e.g., plain text, PAGE XML, METS/ALTO) alongside TEI.

Batch processing: the pipeline could be extended to accept a list of IIF manifest URLs and process them sequentially or in parallel.

7.4 Contribution to the H2IOSC Ecosystem

This workflow represents the first fully operational instance of cross-infrastructure service orchestration within the H2IOSC Marketplace. It demonstrates that the orchestration framework conceived by OPERAS-IT [1, 2, 3] can be implemented in practice using the WSO2-based

methodology described in [4], and that existing open-standard services can be integrated without modification.

The workflow will be published in the H2IOSC Marketplace catalogue as a workflow item, with full documentation of its input parameters, output format, and constituent services. Researchers will be able to trigger it through the Marketplace interface without needing to interact with the individual services or understand the orchestration logic.

The workflow architecture and the orchestration patterns demonstrated in this case study are designed to be adopted by all infrastructure nodes participating in the H2IOSC federation, including DARIAH-IT, CLARIN-IT, and E-RIHS.it. Infrastructure-specific workflow platforms – whether operating as standalone composition environments or as nodes within the broader orchestration framework – can integrate with the Marketplace using the same methodology and standards described here. The pipeline will be published and executable through the H2IOSC Marketplace at <https://marketplace.h2iosc.cnr.it>.

8. Conclusions

This paper has presented a fully automated workflow for historical manuscript transcription and publication, orchestrating IIF, eScriptorium, and TEI Publisher through WSO2 Micro Integrator. The pipeline reduces a multi-step manual process to a single API call, producing a scholarly digital edition with line-image correspondence from a IIF manifest URL.

The key contributions are:

1. A complete, operational implementation of the OPERAS-IT orchestration framework applied to a concrete Digital Humanities workflow, demonstrating the feasibility of cross-infrastructure service orchestration in the SSH domain.
2. A four-phase asynchronous polling pattern for managing the eScriptorium processing pipeline (import, segment, transcribe, export), implemented using WSO2's Message Store and Sampling Message Processor.
3. An XSLT transformation converting ALTO XML to TEI P5 with facsimile encoding, preserving line-level spatial coordinates for scholarly verification.
4. A fully parameterized, runtime-configurable pipeline that can be reused across different corpora, service instances, and infrastructure environments without modification.
5. An assessment of MI Copilot's effectiveness for AI-assisted development of research workflow orchestration artifacts, finding it valuable for scaffolding but insufficient for complex asynchronous patterns and domain-specific transformations.

The orchestration concept and architecture described in this paper was conceived and developed by OPERAS-IT / CNR-ILIESI within the H2IOSC project, as documented in the timeline presented in Figure 1.

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